

Testing Weight-Based Nuclear Criticality Validation Models on the VALID Criticality Benchmarks

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ABSTRACT

In this work, the similarity metrics c_k and E are examined in the benchmark selection process for validating nuclear criticality calculations. Whether requiring additional physical or neutronic similarity improves the process is tested using SCALE/VALID benchmarks. The bias predictive performance is analyzed using the criticality benchmarks as test cases. The bias is modeled using weighted methods: (1) the NUREG/CR-7311 weighted average model (using uncertainty-based weights) and (2) a machine learning (ML) weighted k-nearest neighbors model (wKNN) (using similarity-based weights). The bias variance reduction shows that using c_k outperforms using E ; additionally, the wKNN outperforms the simple weighted average model. No clear similarity threshold emerged. Also, thermal systems showed dependence on the similarity level, whereas fast systems showed little or no such dependence. Requiring benchmarks to have the same neutron spectrum as the application appears unnecessary— c_k sufficiently differentiates these systems. Variance reduction and prediction error showed effectiveness in evaluating the benchmark selection and bias modeling processes and potentially the appropriate sample size as well.

Keywords: criticality, validation, similarity, SCALE, VALID

1. INTRODUCTION

Validation of nuclear criticality safety (NCS) calculations involves selecting benchmark experiments similar to the application and then using them to estimate k_{eff} bias and its uncertainty to derive an upper subcritical limit (USL) [1]. The bias is the systematic difference between the calculations (C) and the measurements (M). The requirement for similar experiments assumes that (1) uncertainties cause biases between k_{eff} calculations and measurements and (2) cases affected by similar uncertainties or having similar physical and neutronic traits exhibit or share similar biases.

Numerous methods are in use for both steps. Engineering judgment is used to select benchmarks based on shared physical and neutronic properties [1], in addition to methods based on nuclear data (ND)-induced similarities [2]. The ND-based correlation-of- k_{eff} (c_k) and the projection between the ND-based sensitivities (E) are used to select benchmarks, applying empirical or calibrated cutoffs. Also, the prediction methods (the second step) range from statistical modeling, such as weighted averaging and regression, to more recent Bayesian techniques [3], [4], [5].

Beyond engineering judgment, it is unclear whether the physical properties of the application must match those of the benchmarks or how high similarity must be for validation to be credible. The

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effectiveness of similarity metrics (e.g., c_k) in modeling the k_{eff} bias is also not fully established. This lack of clarity has contributed to the proliferation of varied validation methodologies.

This work examines selection and modeling approaches that incorporate both similarity metrics and physical constraints, focusing on weighting-based models:

- (1) Uncertainty-based weighting, as outlined in NUREG/CR-7311 [3], using a model that assigns higher weights to benchmarks having lower uncertainty.
- (2) Machine learning (ML) weighted k-nearest neighbors (wKNN) model [6], which assigns weights based on similarity distance (i.e., highly similar benchmarks get higher weights).

Bias predictive performance is evaluated using variance reduction and prediction error across similarity levels and benchmark categories. The analysis indicates that using c_k outperforms using E (although a clear cutoff is not observed). The analysis also provide insight into the relevance of physical constraints in benchmark selection: Spectrum matching appears to be redundant when c_k is used, and fissile material matching offers marginal gains. These findings support the potential of similarity-based modeling to inform validation decisions, identify relevant validation features, and reduce unnecessary conservatism.

2. VALIDATION DATA

Critical benchmarks from the VALID library [7] were analyzed (see Table I). There are 602 criticality measurements on 114 unique critical assemblies or evaluations. The c_k and E are based on the TSUNAMI-IP module of the SCALE code system (version 6.2 [8]). Calculated k_{eff} values and their sensitivity are based on the KENO-VI and the TSUNAMI-3D codes. Measured k_{eff} values, their uncertainties, and the spectral indices (energy of the average lethargy causing fission [EALF] and average neutron energy causing fission [AFGE]) were obtained from the International Criticality Safety Benchmark Evaluation Project (ICSBEP) database [9]. EALF and AFGE are strongly correlated, both replaced in the analysis by their principal component (PC). The training data consist of (1) level variables (fissile material, physical form, and the spectrum), (2) continuous variables (c_k , E , and the $PC_{EALF,AFGE}$), and (3) the critical assembly identifier as metadata.

Table I. Analyzed VALID benchmarks [7].

Identification	Cases	Number of cases
Fissile material	HEU, IEU, LEU, mixed, Pu	162, 69, 198, 61, 112
Physical form	Compound, metal, solution	204, 162, 236
Neutron spectrum	Thermal, fast, intermediate and mixed	471, 123, 8

3. BIAS MODELS

The calculated k_{eff} values are adjusted for the slightly supercritical or subcritical experiments by normalizing the calculated values to the experimental ones to be consistent with the application of NUREG/CR-7311 [3]. Therefore, $C/E = k_{norm} = k_{eff,c} / k_{eff,e}$. In the following sections, k_{norm} denotes the C/E ratio.

The R language [10], along with the caret and kkn packages, is used to apply a weighted-mean (WM) model from NUREG/CR-7311 [3] using the total benchmark uncertainty (σ_i) and its components: uncertainties in the measurements and calculations (σ_E and σ_C , respectively):

$$\bar{k}_{norm} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^K w_i k_{norm,i}}{W}, \quad w_i = \frac{1}{\sigma_i^2} = \frac{1}{\sigma_C^2 + \sigma_E^2} \quad (1)$$

Taking credit of the positive bias is not typically applied in practice, requiring justification of applicability and demonstration that the causes of the bias are known [1], [3]. Its credit aims to eliminate a potential source of non-conservatism. The positive mean bias is credited in the current study to obtain

best estimates rather than conservative ones. The bias is then $\bar{k}_{norm} - 1$, where \bar{k}_{norm} is the average of the calculated-to-measured values.

The second model is an ML wKNN model [6], applied in the benchmarks of subgroups 11 and 14 of the Working Party on Nuclear Criticality Safety (WPNCSS). The model calculates a weighted mean k_{norm} using weights based on the similarity distance between benchmarks and applications (test cases herein), applied as follows:

$$\bar{k}_{norm} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^K w_i k_{norm,i}}{W}, \quad w_i = \frac{1}{\lambda} \exp \left[-\frac{\|1 - d_i\|^2}{2\lambda} \right] \quad (2)$$

where d_i is the similarity distance between the application and each benchmark, measured in c_k or E . Also, c_k is the Pearson correlation coefficient between the application and each benchmark resulting from ND uncertainty, and E is the shared sensitivities to ND—projection of the application ND sensitivity vector onto the sensitivity vector for the benchmark:

$$c_k = \frac{S_a \cdot cov_{ND} \cdot S_b^{-1}}{\sigma_a \sigma_b}, \text{ and } E = S_a \cdot S_b^{-1} \quad (3)$$

where S is the k_{eff} ND sensitivity (calculated using the TSUNAMI-3D module [11] and the SCALE ND), and σ is the calculated uncertainty. Both features measure the similarity between applications and benchmarks with respect to the ND, accounting for ND sensitivities and additionally the covariances in c_k .

For benchmark selection, the WM model does not include an implicit mechanism. Instead, physically and neutronically similar benchmarks could be explicitly selected, or empirical rules could be applied such as selecting benchmarks with a similarity greater than 0.9. The wKNN model implicitly incorporates a benchmark selection mechanism. It derives distance-based weights considering only a subset of the validation data—defined in Eq. (2) as K , which is the number of highly similar benchmarks. K is a hyperparameter determined through nested cross-validation (CV). Notably, K does not need to be the same for each benchmark.

4. PREDICTIVE PERFORMANCE

The WM model is applied using a leave-one-out cross-validation (LOOCV) algorithm, iteratively splitting the data into a training set and a single test case, treated as a hypothetical application. The model estimates k_{norm} of the test case. The observed k_{norm} is the true value, and the model output is the prediction. Both are used to obtain the coefficient of determination (R^2), which indicates the proportion of the variance explained by the model, and the root mean square error (RMSE), which quantifies the residual error. Testing proceeds by investigating a grid of c_k cutoffs; thus, the reported error is a validation one, not the generalization error. R^2 and RMSE are defined in terms of the residual sum of squares (RSS) and total sum of squares (TSS):

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{RSS}{TSS}, \quad RMSE = \left(\frac{RSS}{n-p} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}, \quad TSS = \sum (k_{norm,i} - \bar{k}_{norm})^2, \quad RSS = \sum (k_{norm,i} - k_{norm,p})^2 \quad (4)$$

Here, $k_{norm,i}$ is the true value, \bar{k}_{norm} is the average C/E for all the benchmarks, and $\bar{k}_{norm,p}$ is the predicted value applying the model.

For the wKNN model, the hyperparameter K is tuned using an inner 5-fold repeated CV process. Thus, the nested CV setup allows for the estimation of generalization error.

In addition to the mentioned benchmark selection methods, we overlay two approaches:

1. Engineering-based approach: The properties of the benchmarks are model inputs. The benchmarks are required to share specific physical or neutronic properties with the application (in addition to c_k or E similarity)—for example, both having thermal spectra.
2. Model-based approach: The properties of the benchmarks are meta parameters. The models use the similarity-based selection solely; then, the properties of the benchmarks are aggregated to calculate which features are frequently shared between the application and the benchmarks.

5. RESULTS

5.1. WM Model

Figure 1 (left plots) shows R^2 and $RMSE$ of the WM model versus c_k and E cutoffs, indicating that c_k has better predictive capability than E . The subsequent discussion focuses on c_k . Although high similarity resulted in better bias predictions (particularly for $c_k > 0.9$), the overall predictive performance of these models remains low, and there is no indication of an optimal c_k cutoff. The right plots show R^2 and $RMSE$ for the WM model applying the engineering-based benchmark selection. In the high c_k cutoff range, validation using only benchmarks with the same fissile material marginally improves R^2 and reduces $RMSE$. This may justify, for example, explicitly validating LEU or plutonium systems using LEU or plutonium benchmarks, in addition to the c_k similarity. This finding is consistent with the model-based approach (Figure 2), which shows that a portion of the validation data originates from dissimilar fissile systems that are not filtered out by c_k . Requiring matching neutron spectrum does not significantly affect R^2 and $RMSE$ because a high c_k value filters out benchmarks with differing spectra. Thermal and fast systems are already well separated in correlation space (see the bottom-right plot in Figure 2), making additional spectrum-based filtering redundant. Separating the effect of the physical form is not possible because it correlates strongly with the neutron spectrum in the analyzed VALID cases, except at lower c_k cutoff where both the compound and solution systems (both thermal) tend to be similar and validate each other; their separation marginally deteriorates R^2 and increases $RMSE$.

Figure 1. R^2 and $RMSE$ vs. c_k and E cutoffs for models using any benchmark, regardless of their characteristics (left plots). R^2 and $RMSE$ vs. c_k cutoffs, adding a benchmark selection rule (right plots). Dashed lines are for models forcing similarity between cases: fissile material (+F), physical form (+C), and spectrum (+S).

Figure 2. Shared weight fractions between the test benchmarks (hypothetical applications) and the benchmarks having $c_k > \text{cutoff}$ (averaged for each benchmark category). Top row: ratio between the sum of k_{norm} weights of the

benchmarks in the same evaluation to the total sum of weights of all benchmarks—weights are calculated using Eq. (1). Bottom row: ratio between the sum of k_{norm} weights of the benchmarks having the same physical/neutronical properties as the test benchmarks to the total sum of weights of all benchmarks. As the c_k cutoff gets lower, the test cases use more heterogeneous benchmarks in their validation, including other evaluations and benchmarks differing in their physical/neutronical properties.

The predictive performance is shown in Figure 3 for the thermal systems (rightmost plots) as well as solutions and compounds (middle plots, predominantly thermal systems). It shows improved predictive performance at higher c_k cutoffs. Applying a cutoff may have a justifiable basis. Conversely, fast systems (rightmost plots) and metals (middle plots, predominantly fast systems) show little to no improvement in the predictive performance. Applying a cutoff may not be justified, and validation could benefit from using lower or no cutoffs to retain a larger benchmark set.

Figure 3. R^2 vs. c_k cutoffs for selected categories. Solid line is like Figure 1.

Overall, the predictive power is modest (even for the thermal cases) at high c_k of 0.99 and 0.95; R^2 is only 0.51 and 0.37, respectively. The initial bias error decreases from 441 pcm to 308 and 354 pcm, respectively. Figure 5 shows the observed and predicted k_{norm} at a high c_k (0.99) for the WM model (left plot); the figure also includes the corresponding wKNN results, which are discussed in Section 5.2. The WM model predictions indicate a significant systematic error in k_{norm} predictions. Specifically, the residual error (308 pcm) comprises 210 pcm systematic error and 225 pcm random error; 46% of the error is systematic. This suggests that the WM model lacks flexibility to train on the data, motivating analyses of models weighting the similarity.

Applying the WM model along with a high c_k cutoff reduces the bias variance. However, this does not indicate how many benchmarks should be ideally used. Validation should involve many highly correlated benchmarks, but both the number of benchmarks and the c_k cutoff depend on the dataset. For a given validation dataset, higher c_k cutoff results in a lower number of benchmarks being used. This raises the question: Is there an optimal balance between c_k cutoff and the number of benchmarks?

The data are simulated by iterative stratified sampling, progressively diluting the validation data to reduce the benchmarks density (thus reducing the number of benchmarks at equivalent similarity). In each sample, the WM model is applied, and the predictive performance is evaluated. Thus, the number of benchmarks and the c_k cutoff are variables, and the bias prediction error is an optimization target.

Figure 4 shows that lower c_k cutoffs with more benchmarks can result in similar predictive performance comparable to stricter cutoffs with fewer benchmarks. Various combinations of c_k cutoff and number of benchmarks have similar bias predictive capacity. Such analysis requires an initial variance reduction. The baseline model must demonstrate meaningful RMSE for the analysis to be valid. Thus, Figure 4 contains only the thermal benchmarks. On the other side, such analysis is not valid for the fast and metal systems, showing limited initial variance reduction and offering no meaningful trade-off insight.

Figure 4. The number of benchmarks (primary y-axis), c_k cutoff (x-axis), and the bias RMSE (contours). Noise is smoothed out using a Gaussian filter of 2 standard deviations.

5.2. wKNN Model

wKNN models using c_k and E are compared under similar conditions: similarity > 0.9 and at least 10 benchmarks. Similar to the WM model, the wKNN model shows better performance using c_k . R^2 is 0.42–0.43, compared with 0.37 for the E -based model. This suggests that c_k has more relevant information about bias, being a better predictor. The following discussion focuses on the c_k -based models. Feature importance is evaluated firstly using the engineering-based approaches, and the results are summarized in Table II. Compared with the c_k -only model, requiring the same fissile material provides a small improvement in R^2 and RMSE. In contrast, enforcing similarity in physical form or spectrum degrades performance. This suggests that enforcing similarity in redundant features—already captured by c_k —may not benefit the ML model and even reduce performance. This is consistent with the results of the WM model, where fissile classification proved useful, and the spectral one was redundant.

Table II. R^2 and RMSE for wKNN, using c_k solely and applying the engineering approach.

Metric	c_k -model	+Fissile material	+Physical form	+Neutron spectrum
R^2	0.45	0.48	0.35	0.35
RMSE (pcm)	331	321	354	354

Feature importance is evaluated also following the model-based approach. The wKNN model uses the benchmarks' properties as features, and their model sensitivity-based importance is provided in Table III. The sensitivities confirm that c_k is the dominant predictor. The physical form and spectrum categories have low relevance. PCs of spectral indices (EALF and AFG \bar{E}) are more informative than basic classifications (e.g., fast or thermal), likely due to their continuous and system-specific nature. The wKNN model does not exclude features outright, but their contribution is adjusted inherently in the model. Overall, c_k remains the main driver of predictions, with other features contributing marginally.

Table III. Sensitivity-based feature importance ($\times 10^2$) in the basic wKNN model.

Category	c_k	Fissile material	Physical form	Neutron spectrum	PCs
Fast	0.45	0.48	0.35	0.35	0.35
Thermal	331	321	354	354	354

The predictive performance of the wKNN model is comparable to the WM one, with slightly better R^2 . Figure 5 shows predicted versus observed k_{norm} for thermal systems. Despite the improvement, predictions still exhibit a significant systematic error component and potential outlier benchmarks. As with the WM model, predictive performance varies across system categories. Fast systems show little to no improvement. Validating with c_k cutoffs in this regime may not be justifiable. On the other hand, thermal systems and their dominant physical forms (compounds and solutions) demonstrate meaningful and promising variance reduction, consistent with earlier findings on the WM model.

Table IV. Initial (*i*) and final (*f*) RMSE and R^2 by spectrum and physical form categories, where initial and final refer to the k_{norm} errors before and after the application of the wKNN model.

Category	Neutron spectrum		Physical form		
	Fast	Thermal	Compound	Solution	Metal
RMSE _i (pcm)	398	446	320	547	382
RMSE _f (pcm)	409	325	210	412	377
R^2	0.01	0.47	0.59	0.45	0.06

Figure 5. Predicted vs. observed k_{norm} of thermal systems for the WM model ($c_k > 0.99$) (left) and wKNN (right).

Overall, the wKNN model offers modest advantages over the WM model in terms of bias predictive performance. It is also capable of internally identifying relevant features and tuning their contribution, and it requires less manual or empirical interference on the number of benchmarks (ranging between 9 and 13 benchmarks) or the similarity cutoff, being based on nested CV.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The study tested using the c_k and E similarity metrics in selecting benchmarks from the VALID data for criticality validation purposes. The bias was modeled using an uncertainty-based weighted average model (WM), compared with similarity-based modeling using the wKNN ML model. Using c_k consistently outperforms using E , supporting the account for the ND covariances in NCS validation. The wKNN model provides slightly better performance than the WM model, demonstrating the potential of feature and similarity weighting. Requiring cases to have the same fissile material led to modest improvement in the prediction accuracy, whereas enforcing similarity in neutron spectrum or physical form showed no benefit, likely because they are already captured by the c_k and are thus correlated or redundant.

The necessity of a meaningful variance reduction is highlighted. For example, thermal systems showed better bias predictability with increasing c_k cutoff, whereas fast metal systems did not. Thus, using c_k

cutoff for the thermal systems is justified, and it lacks basis for the fast ones. The variance reduction in the thermal systems also allowed finding combinations of the c_k cutoffs and the number of benchmarks that are comparable in their bias predictive performance. Again, fast systems lack such analysis.

Generalizability is limited by the small data size, the strong correlation between some of the features, and the lack of correlations between the measurements conducted in the same evaluation. Thus, future work will focus on expanding the VALID data, further analysis of models weighting the similarity, and better evaluation of experimental correlations and their incorporation into the validation models.

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